

ISSN 0976-5484

SOCIAL WORK JOURNAL

(BI-ANNUAL)**Volume 9****Number 2****July-December 2018**

- Editorial - Prof. M. Gangabhusan & Dr. G. Albin Joseph
- Rekindling the Spirit of Adventure among the North East India's Youth in their Dreams of Ventures: A Study on the Role of MUDRA Bank - Mr. Happyson Gachuiwo & Dr. A.S. Yarso
- Problems and Prospects to Development of North-East India - Mr. T Luithuiwung Awungshi & Dr. G. Albin Joseph
- Entrepreneurship- An Alternative in Manipur - Mr. Md Akbar Khan
- Impact of Social Media: A Study on the Tribal Youth Entrepreneurs of Manipur - Mr. Abel Ariina & Dr. G Albin Joseph
- Prevention of Substance Use Disorder and Associated High-Risk Behaviours among Youths through Social Work Intervention - Mr. Sathish Kumar R & Dr. K. Sathyamurthi
- Media and Drug Abuse: A Study of Tangkhul Naga Youth of Ukhrul District, Manipur. -Mr. T Luithuiwung Awungshi & Dr. G. Albin Joseph
- Families of people with intellectual impairment: Siblings' Paradox as Future Care Givers - Mr. Ujjwal Swaroop K, Ms. Vijayalakshmi T & Prof. R.D.Sampath Kumar
- The Becoming of a 'Bride': Compelling Circumstances and Complexities - Ms. Priyanka Patowari, Dr. Ratna Huiem, and Dr. Kathiresan L.
- Mainstreaming At Risk Youth by Engaging in Civic Activities through Social Workers - Dr. Aditi Nath
- The Purity- Impurity Conundrum: Examining the Availability of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Conditions in the Borjalenga Rajubari Community –Ajit Kumar Jena
- Religiosity and Life Satisfaction of the Older Persons in Mizoram
Jennifer Rohlupuii* & Easwaran Kanagaraj **

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL WORK
ASSAM UNIVERSITY, SILCHAR – 788011
INDIA. Phone: +91 3842 270821

ISSN 0976-5484

SOCIAL WORK JOURNAL

(BI-ANNUAL)

Volume 9

Number 2

July- December 2018

Published by

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL WORK

ASSAM UNIVERSITY, SILCHAR – 788011

Assam. INDIA. Phone: +91 3842 270821

www.aus.ac.in

SOCIAL WORK JOURNAL
(Bi-annual)
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar – 788011, Assam, India

EDITORS

Dr. M. GANGABHUSHAN
Professor & Head
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. G. ALBIN JOSEPH
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

EDITORIAL BOARD

Prof. Gopal Ji Mishra
Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Prof. Subhabrata Dutta
Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Prof. M. Tineshowri Devi
Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Tarun Bikash Sukal
Associate Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Mrityunjay Kr. Singh
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Ratna Hulrem
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Kathiresan L.
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Kaivalya T. Desai
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Ritwika Rajendra
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Lalzo S. Thangjom
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Aditi Nath
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Mr. Ajit Jena
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

Dr. Joyashri Dey
Assistant Professor
Department of Social Work
Assam University, Silchar

ADVISORY BOARD

Prof. K.V. Ramana
Former Vice Chancellor
Andhra University
Vishakhapatnam, AP

Prof. C.S. Ramanathan
Human Service Enterprise
MI, USA

Prof. K.V. Nagaraj
Department of Mass Communications
Mizoram University, Aizawl, Mizoram

Prof. B.T. Lawani
Former Director, Social Sciences Centre
Bharati Vidyapeeth University, Pune,
MH

Prof. B.S. Gunjal
Department of Social Work
Kuvempu University, Shimoga,
Karnataka

Prof. R. Parthasarathy
Department of Psychiatric Social Work
NIMHANS, Bangalore, Karnataka

SOCIAL WORK JOURNAL (BI-ANNUAL)

Volume 9, Issue 2, July-December 2018

CONTENTS

Sl. No.	Title	Author(s)	Page No.
	Editorial	Prof. M. Gangabhusan & Dr. G. Albin Joseph	5
1	Rekindling the Spirit of Adventure among the North East India's Youth in their Dreams of Ventures: A Study on the Role of MUDRA Bank	Mr. Happyson Gachuiwo & Dr. A.S. Yarso	7
2	Problems and Prospects to Development of North-East India	Mr. T Luithuiwung Awungshi & Dr. G. Albin Joseph	17
3	Entrepreneurship- An Alternative in Manipur	Mr. Md Akbar Khan	26
4	Impact of Social Media: A Study on the Tribal Youth Entrepreneurs of Manipur	Mr. Abel Ariina & Dr. G Albin Joseph	35
5	Prevention of Substance Use Disorder and Associated High-Risk Behaviours among Youth through Social Work Intervention	Mr. Sathish Kumar R & Dr. K. Sathyamurthi	45
6	Media and Drug Abuse: A Study of Tangkhul Naga Youth of Ukhrul District, Manipur.	Mr. T Luithuiwung Awungshi & Dr. G. Albin Joseph	55
7	Families of people with intellectual impairment: Siblings' Paradox as Future Care Givers	Mr. Ujjwal Swaroop K, Ms. Vijayalakshmi T & Prof. R.D.Sampath Kumar	63
8	The Becoming of a 'Bride': Compelling Circumstances and Complexities	Ms. Priyanka Patowari, Dr. Ratna Huirem, and Dr. Kathiresan L.	82
9	Mainstreaming at Risk Youth by Engaging in Civic Activities through Social Workers	Dr. Aditi Nath	91
10	The Purity- Impurity Conundrum: Examining the Availability of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Conditions in the Borjalenga Rajubari Community	Ajit Kumar Jena	98
11	Religiosity and Life Satisfaction of the Older Persons in Mizoram	Jennifer Rohlupuii* & Easwaran Kanagaraj *	105

Editorial

We are happy to bring out the current issue of Social Work Journal of Department of Social Work, Assam University. This issue is predominantly covering papers centred on the youth, entrepreneurship, development and disability studies.

The paper on “Rekindling the Spirit of Adventure among the North East India’s Youth in their Dreams of Ventures: A Study on the Role of MUDRA Bank” by Happyson Gachuiwo and A.S. Yarso describes the scheme of MUDRA Bank which was launched by the Government of India and more specifically to sensitize the provisions and offerings of this scheme for start-up rural entrepreneurs of North East India.

In the paper on “Problems and Prospects to Development of North-East India” the authors T Luithuiwung Awungshi and G. Albin Joseph discuss the problems, issues and potential resources of North Eastern Region by using SWOT analysis and suggest remedial measures for development.

The article entitled “Entrepreneurship: An Alternative in Manipur” authored by Md. Akbar Khan gives a brief analysis the role of entrepreneur in the state of Manipur and the factors that triggered the individuals to start their own enterprises. It also seeks to understand the correlation of societal factors and the entrepreneurship.

Another paper entitled “Impact of Social Media: A Study on the Tribal Youth Entrepreneurs of Manipur” jointly authored by Abel Ariina and G Albin Joseph reiterates the role of social media as one of the most important tools to promote marketing avenues of the youth entrepreneurs and have the potential to transform the mode of business through shaping the public perception of entrepreneurs and the start-ups process.

“Prevention of Substance Use Disorder and Associated High-Risk Behaviours among Youths through Social Work Intervention” by Sathish Kumar R and K Sathyamurthi brings forward the factors and high risk behaviours that are associated with substance use disorder among youths of T.P.Chatiram, Chennai. It also advocates for the role of social work practitioners in addressing the issues of substance use disorder and the associated high-risk behaviours.

T Luithuiwung Awunghsi and G. Albin Joseph through their paper entitled “Media and Drug Abuse: A Study of Tangkhul Naga Youth of Ukhrul District, Manipur” try to give an overview of the attitudinal behavioral of Ukhrul youth toward media related to drug abuse with substantial suggestions regarding media and youth drug abuse.

The paper entitled “Families of people with intellectual impairment: Siblings’ Paradox as Future Care Givers” is an outcome of an empirical study in the Visakhapatnam District of Andhra Pradesh by Ujjwal Swaroop K, Vijayalakshmi T and R.D. Sampath Kumar which focused on the socio-cultural and psychological factors contributing to the services, offered to the intellectually impaired persons by the parents, NGOs and Government.

The paper entitled “The Becoming of a ‘Bride’: Compelling Circumstances and Complexities” by Priyanka Patowari, Ratna Huirem and Kathiresan L is an important contribution focusing on the problems associated with early marriages from gender perspective. They tries to unpack the social realities that encumber upon a young girl thus forcing her to enter into matrimony much before she can comprehend the whole meaning of the word “marriage”. It also deals with the complexities of being a child bride.

Aditi Nath in her paper “Mainstreaming at Risk Youth by Engaging in Civic Activities through Social Workers” advocates the role civic engagements as an approach of risk reduction and the role of social work in promoting civic activities for at risk youth development. The author substantiates and advocates for promoting social activities for generating civic awareness among at risk youth found to be helpful in building confidence, developing leadership skill, strengthening relationships, and make a strong civic identity.

The paper entitled “The Purity- Impurity Conundrum: Examining the Availability of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Conditions in the Borjalenga Rajubari Community” by Ajit Kumar Jena attempts to examine the availability of safe drinking water, hygiene conditions and challenges of rural people in Borjalenga Rajubari Community.

Finally, the paper entitled “Religiosity and Life Satisfaction of the Older Persons in Mizoram” authored by Jennifer Rohlupuii & Easwaran Kanagaraj reiterates the relationship between the Religion and the Life satisfaction of the Older persons.

M. Gangabhusan

G. Albin Joseph

Religiosity and Life Satisfaction of the Older Persons in Mizoram

Jennifer Rohlupui* & Easwaran Kanagaraj**

Abstract

Life satisfaction is a global assessment of a person's quality of life according to his/her chosen criteria. It is a significant indicator to ascertain the quality of life of senior citizens. The terms "religiousness" or "religiosity" reflect the amount of importance of religion in the life of the person. Some studies have shown that religiosity, religious participation in churches and attending other religious services play a positive role in the search for meaning and purpose in life for senior citizens. Religious participation is positively associated with both the quantity and the quality of the social relationship. Mizoram is a relatively small state in North-East India with a rapidly urbanizing trend and senior citizens constantly have to re-orient themselves to changes in society. The size of the older population (60 years and above) in Mizoram constitutes 5.5% of the total population. Mizos are predominantly Christian and are religious. Religious activities and participation play an important role in their daily lives. In this context, this paper seeks to examine the religious participation of senior citizens and its relation to their life satisfaction. The study is cross-sectional in nature and descriptive in design and is based on quantitative data collected through pre-tested structured interview schedule from the rural and urban populations of senior citizens in Aizawl district. The study reveals that Religious Participation and Life Satisfaction among the senior citizens are associated with location, denomination and family income. However, there is no gender difference in Religious Participation or Life Satisfaction. Senior citizens in urban areas have greater Religious Participation and Life Satisfaction as compared to those in rural areas. Age has a negative effect on Religious Participation but no significant difference in Life Satisfaction. Size of the family has a significant positive effect on Religious Participation but a negative effect on Life Satisfaction.

The present paper attempts to assess the relationship between religious participation and life satisfaction of senior citizens in Mizoram.

Ageing is a universal biological and natural process. In biological terms, ageing is a dynamic process that represents the molecular, biochemical, physiological and structural changes that take place in an

* Jennifer Rohlupui, UGC Senior Research Fellow, Department of Social Work, Mizoram University, Aizawl-796004.

Email: jenniferrohluui@gmail.com

** Prof. Kanagaraj Easwaran, Professor, Department of Social Work, Mizoram University, Aizawl - 796004.

individual following the cessation of growth (Dey, 2003). For Asian societies, the issues related to senior citizens need immediate attention of researchers, planners, and welfare agencies. China and India, Asia's most populous nations, are estimated to contribute a significant proportion of this growing number of older people (Irudaya-Rajan, Misra & Sarma, 2001).

The major goal of social workers working with senior citizens at the multi-level has been the promotion of their well-being. Life satisfaction is one of the ways of assessing the subjective well-being of individuals. Life satisfaction is a global assessment of a person's quality of life according to his chosen criteria (Shin & Johnson, 1978). Life satisfaction often refers to the attitudes that individuals have about their past, present as well as future in relation to their psychological well being (Chadha & Van Willigen, 1995).

Religion and spirituality play such important roles in our lives and it is vital for social workers to understand how it affects their clients and how it can be used to help them in their personal growth and progress in their mental health. As social workers moved toward a more professional approach, they began distancing themselves from religion and spirituality, by adopting more secular approaches. Kaplan & Dziegielewski (1999) suggests that this happened in order to fit in with the science-based professions of psychology and psychiatry; which state that spiritual beliefs are not by nature empirical. She goes on to say that this is a significant problem since one of the cornerstones of social work is that it recognizes the whole person and the influences in their lives; spirituality being a major component.

Many people especially senior citizen's use of spirituality as a weapon in their coping arsenal is precisely why spirituality must be acknowledged. Strengthening their abilities to develop viable strategies to both meet basic needs and maintain mental health is a social work goal. Many social workers find religion and spirituality to be a fundamental part of their client's lives and see these aspects as completely appropriate to address in therapy (Coholic, 2003) and many clinicians are already practising with religious and spiritual intervention but without feeling properly equipped. In response, the Council of Social Work Education (CSWE) has begun to introduce spiritual and religious practice into their

accreditation standards (Council of Social Work Education, 2001). The Council of Social Work Education (2001) maintains that social workers need to be able to work with clients with understanding and without discrimination regarding religious and spiritual practices.

Social workers are ethically responsible to be prepared to respond (competently) and effectively to spiritual and religious beliefs, behaviors and traditions which are common within much of human experience (micro and macro), while recognizing that beliefs, behaviours and traditions often form a framework which is used to interpret and make meaning of experience.

Religion and spirituality are a vital part of many people's lives and plays a significant role in how many deals with life's ups and downs. Therefore, more attention should be paid to religion and spirituality in order to better prepare social workers and meet the client's needs.

Overview of Literature

Religion especially religious beliefs and participation are found to have a significant positive effect on the life satisfaction of the people. The terms "religiousness" or "religiosity" reflect the amount of importance of religion in the life of the person, but terms like "religious life review" or "religious maturity" reflect applications of religion in the person's life (Ellor and McGregor, 2011). Religion offers a way to express spirituality with social support, security, a sense of belonging through religious affiliations and is significant in coping with age-related changes. (Lezotte, 2010). Religious and spiritual interventions have been found to positively affect people's lives to repair mental health problems when used alone or combined with other interventions. Elderly people who claim to have higher levels of religious beliefs and activities were noted to have improved psychological health than those with lower religious activities and beliefs (Morse & Wisocki, 1987). Studies reveal that religious people are more satisfied with their lives because they regularly attend religious services and build social networks in their congregations (Lim & Putnam, 2010). Studies also suggest that strong religious faith and personal spiritual experiences can improve well-being by bolstering self-esteem and self-efficacy (Ellison 1991). More research reveals that interviews with women aged 65 to 98 have more time and felt freer to explore their prayer life than

younger women; ageing had allowed their prayers to become simpler, spontaneous, intimate, more meaningful, and personal and open with God as a valued companion (Melia, 2001).

An overview of literature on the religiosity of the senior citizens suggests that the research on the religiosity of the senior citizens is still in its infancy. Each of its aspects studied to date needs further explorations to confirm, modify, or correct current findings. It also shows that there are a few studies on religiosity and its relationship with the well-being of the senior citizen's in the contexts of India, it's North East region especially Mizoram. The present study tries to fill these research gaps.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To assess life satisfaction among senior citizens in Mizoram
2. To study the differences in religious participation between senior citizens living in rural and urban areas in Mizoram
3. To study the differences in religious participation across gender among senior citizens
4. To probe into the relationship between religious participation and life satisfaction

Methodology

The study is cross-sectional in nature and descriptive in design. It is based on quantitative data collected through field survey with pre-tested structured interview schedule from the rural and urban populations of senior citizens in Aizawl district.

The unit of the study is individual senior citizen aged 60 years and above. Aizawl district has been selected based on the highest population concentration of senior citizens in the state of Mizoram (GoM 2010).

The study used a Multi-Stage Sampling procedure to select district, localities and individual respondents. The universe consists of all Mizo senior citizens above the age of 60 years in Mizoram. In the first stage, Aizawl district has been chosen purposively based on the highest population concentration of senior citizens as per Statistical Handbook Mizoram 2010. In the second stage, stratified sampling has been applied. Rural and Urban localities were drawn based on socio-economic development indicators at the village level. Three Urban localities and three

rural villages which have socio-economic development index values closer to urban area average index were selected.

In the third stage, lists of all member of Mizoram Upa Pawl (Senior Citizens' Association in Mizoram) in the selected villages and localities identified were collected. In each of the selected localities, 30 per cent of the senior citizens (+60 yrs) residing in that village or locality were taken using systematic random sampling.

Structured interview schedule has been constructed to obtain quantitative data on the demographic social and economic profile of the respondents, religious participation, and satisfaction with life. For assessing religious participation, a scale was constructed with six items and used. For assessing life satisfaction, personal well-being and satisfaction with life scale (Satisfaction with Life as a Whole and The Personal Well-Being Index Scale by International Well-being Group (2006) Part – 2) was used.

The reliability of the two scales was assessed with the help of three measures viz., Alpha, Guttman, Split-half and Parallel and the reliability coefficients were found very high. The reliability coefficients of Alpha (0.76), Guttman Split-half (0.81), parallel - estimated reliability of scale (0.76), Parallel - the unbiased estimate of reliability (0.76) for religious participation scale were found to be high (above 0.75). Similarly, the reliability coefficients of Alpha (0.90), Guttman Split-half (0.90), parallel - Estimated reliability of scale (0.90), and parallel - unbiased estimate of reliability (0.90) for life satisfaction scale were found to be high (above 0.75) (see table 1).

For assessing the validity apart from face validity with experts, factor analysis with principal components method was used. The factor analysis showed that the items in both the scales have high factor loadings and established the convergent validity of the scales (see tables 2 and 3).

The quantitative data collected through field survey was processed with computer packages of MS Excel and SPSS. For analysis of data simple averages, cross tabulation, percentages, t-test, Karl Pearson's Product moment correlation and multiple linear regression analysis were used.

Results and Discussion

The data analysis includes 288 senior citizens above the age of 60 years. Three (3) rural villages namely Thanglailung, North Khawlek, Luangpawm and three (3) urban localities namely Ramhlun Venglai, Ramthar North and Zemabawk have been selected.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic characteristics discussed here include age, marital status, educational status, size of family and locality.

Some gerontologists have recognized the diversity of old age by defining it into three categories: young-old, middle-old and old-old. In the present study, the age of the senior citizens has been classified using these three categories.

Age group has been found as one of the variables having a significant association with life satisfaction of the elderly. Cross-sectional studies have presented results ranging from finding no relationship at all between age and life satisfaction (Diener et al., 1999; Hamarat et al., 2002) to finding a positive relationship (Diener, 1984; Mercier et al., 1998; Prenda & Lachman, 2001) and even negative relationships (Chen, 2001; Freund & Baltes, 1998). In one of the few studies applying a longitudinal design, Mroczek & Spiro (2005) found a decrease in life satisfaction in very old age. Findings from various studies of later life are contradictory.

The study reveals that among the young-old, middle-old and old-old there is no difference in age distribution. The total population in the urban area is more; therefore the number of senior citizens in the urban area is also more as compared to rural areas. Majority of the male respondents are married, whereas the percentages of widows are high more among the female respondents. In terms of educational status, male respondents have higher education than female and there are more illiterates among female respondents. There is no significant difference in terms of the size of the family.

Social and Economic Profile of the Respondents

Among all the denominations in Mizoram, a majority of the respondents belong to the Presbyterian denomination, followed by the United Pentecostal Church of Mizoram.

Financial satisfaction measured as the perception of economic deprivation has been found to be related to lower satisfaction with life (Revicki & Mitchell, 1990). Therefore, financial security seems to constitute an important component of life satisfaction in old age. Although well-being does not increase with more money to spend, the experience of financial insecurity probably represents a basic menace to life satisfaction even in old age.

In this study, in terms of economic conditions, the majority of the household earn between Rs.10000 – Rs.20000 and men have greater income as compared to women.

Religious Participation

Religious participation is positively associated with both the quantity and the quality of social relationship (Ellison & George, 1994). Studies diverge as to why people who are committed to their religion especially those who regularly attend services and participate in religious activities have a higher level of subjective well-being and life satisfaction. One explanation is that it offers social support and network. Krause and Wulff (2005) propose that church-based friendship may promote a sense of belonging and thus enhance physical and mental health. In a subsequent study based on elderly Christians, Krause (2003) finds a positive relationship between involvement with church friends and life satisfaction.

Gender and Religious Participation

In a study conducted by Zhang(2010) women reported a higher proportion of religious participation, but the cognitive benefits of religious participation were stronger for men. However, in this present study, there is no significant difference in religious participation (see table 6).

Geographical Location and Religious Participation

In a study conducted by Krause et al (2010) among senior citizens of Japan, older people in rural areas are more deeply involved in religion than older people who live in more urbanized areas.

However, this study reveals quite the opposite. Table 7 shows that the senior citizens in the urban areas have significantly greater religious participation as compared their rural counterparts.

Determinants of Religious Participation

A multiple linear regression model was fitted to see the effect of demographic, social and economic factors on religious participation of the senior citizens. The dependent variable was weighted religious participation score derived from factor analysis of items included in the scale constructed. The explanatory variables include Age Group, Gender (Female =1, 0 otherwise), Denomination (Presbyterian = 1, 0 otherwise), Living with Spouse (Yes =1, otherwise = 0), Educational Status (levels of education), Geographical Location (Rural = 1, otherwise = 0), Size of Family, type of Family (Joint =1, otherwise = 0), Monthly Household Income (levels of income), and Monthly Personal Income (levels of income)(see table).

The multiple linear regression model of determinants of religious participation of the senior citizens were having a very poor fit. The F ratio (2.38) was significant at 5 per cent level and the explanatory variables could explain only 5 per cent of the variation in the explained variable i.e. religious participation.

Religious participation of the senior citizens in the context of Mizoram is found to significantly associate with geographical location (2.48) and size of family (2.03). The senior citizens in the urban areas have significantly greater religious participation as compared their rural counterparts when the effects of demographic, social and economic factors in the model are controlled for.

Size of the family had a significant positive effect on the religious participation of the senior citizens. It means that religious participation increases with the size of the family of the respondents.

The demographic variables viz., Age Group, Gender and Educational Status (levels of education) have no significant effect on religious participation of the elderly even at 5 per cent level. Likewise, the social structural factors of Denomination, Living with Spouse, and Type of Family had no significant effect on religious participation. Further, the economic factors viz., Monthly Household Income, and Monthly Personal Income had no significant effect on religious participation(see table 8).

Gender and Life Satisfaction

Many studies have found that there are gender differences in level of life satisfaction as women experience more health-related problems than men (Gold, Malmberg, McClearn, Pedersen, & Berg, 2002; Murtagh & Hubert, 2004), however, some recent studies reveal that there are fewer gender differences in level of life satisfaction.

In this study, we can see that there is no significant gender difference in terms of life satisfaction (see table 9).

Geographic Location and Life Satisfaction

Priyanka and Sunita (2013) among senior citizens in urban and semi-urban families of Lucknow. Results revealed that no significant differences were found in overall life satisfaction of elderly people in urban and semi-urban dwellings.

However, as we can see in Table 10, the present study shows that respondents in urban areas have a higher level of life satisfaction as compared to respondents in rural areas.

Determinants of Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction among senior citizens is an important concept as it gives an overall view of the adjustment as well as the adaptive coping ability of the individual. The results from the few studies conducted among senior citizens indicate stability (Diener, Suh, Lucas, & Smith, 1999) or even an increase in life satisfaction (Diener, 1984; Mercier, Peladeau, & Tempier, 1998), whereas other studies suggest a decrease (Mroczek & Spiro, 2005). Senior citizens are especially exposed to numerous potential threats to life satisfaction such as loss of the spouse, changes in daily activities, changes in the social network, and age-related diseases.

Table 11 reveals that demographic factors have no effect on life satisfaction. Age and gender have no significant effect on life satisfaction. Education has an unexpectedly negative effect on life satisfaction, which means that the higher the education, the lower life satisfaction. However, in comparison with urban areas, rural areas have lower life satisfaction. Monthly personal income and household income has a positive effect on life satisfaction

The study provides a higher understanding of the life satisfaction of senior citizens in the Christian community and presented a novel finding of

religiosity and religious participation being significantly correlated with their satisfaction of life.

Religious Participation and Life Satisfaction

The focus of the present study is the hypothesis that religious participation and life satisfaction of the senior citizens is directly related controlling for the effects of the demographic, familial, social and economic structural factors. A multiple linear regression model was fitted to see to test this hypothesis. The dependent variable was weighted life satisfaction score derived from factor analysis of items included in the scale. The explanatory variables include the demographic, familial, social, economic structural variables and religious participation. The demographic variables are Age Group, Gender (Female =1, 0 otherwise), Educational Status (levels of education), familial structural variables include Living with Spouse (Yes =1, otherwise = 0), Size of Family, and type of Family (Joint =1, otherwise = 0). Denomination (Presbyterian = 1, 0 otherwise) and Geographical Location (Rural = 1, otherwise = 0) were the two social structural variables while economic variables include Monthly Household Income (levels of income), Monthly Personal Income (levels of income). Apart from these Religious Participation scores was also included (see table).

The multiple linear regression model of determinants of life satisfaction of the senior citizens was having a moderate level of fit. The F ratio (18.54) was significant at 1 per cent level and the explanatory variables could explain about 40 per cent of the variation in the explained variable life satisfaction of the senior citizens.

As expected the religious participation has a significant positive effect on life satisfaction of senior citizens, controlling for the effects of demographic, familial, social, and economic structural variables. In other words, higher religious participation greater is the life satisfaction of the senior citizens. Hence, the hypothesis that religious participation and life satisfaction of the senior citizens is directly related controlling for the effects of the demographic, familial, social and economic structural factors has been validated.

The demographic structural variables viz., age group and gender have no significant effect on the life satisfaction of the elderly while educational status has a negative effect on life satisfaction. This is contrary to the expectation. None of the familial structural variables living with Spouse, Size of Family, and Type of Family had any significant relationship with life satisfaction.

On the other hand, both the social structural factors denomination and geographical location had a significant effect on the life satisfaction of the elderly. The members of the numerically predominant denomination i.e. the Presbyterian Church had better life satisfaction as compared to those of other denominations. The respondents from urban areas have significantly greater life satisfaction as compared to their counterparts in rural areas.

Interestingly, the economic structural variables viz., monthly household income, and monthly personal income have a significant positive effect on the life satisfaction of the elderly in Mizoram. In other words, higher the monthly income of the household and monthly personal income of the respondents higher was his/her life satisfaction when all the effects of demographic, familial and social structural factors as well as religious participation are controlled for.

Conclusion

Religious practices and participation occupy a key place in the life of the Mizos. It is an established fact that older people if they are given the opportunity, to participate actively in the life of the community as well as the church as it gives them a sense of belonging, self-worth and life satisfaction. However, many of them are unable to actively participate due to the deterioration of physical health. The results of multivariate analysis demonstrate the positive influence of religious participation on the life satisfaction of older persons has been demonstrated in the context of the Christianized tribal society of Mizoram controlling for a number of demographic, social and economic structural factors. Interestingly, economic factors viz., household income and personal income have a significant positive effect on the life satisfaction of senior citizens.

Professional social workers working with senior citizens in Christian communities must acknowledge and give due emphasize the role

of spiritual, religious aspects in their life. However, their material well-being need not be overlooked and efforts of promoting the material and spiritual well-being of the senior citizens be combined. Professional social workers in Mizoram need to advocate for the provision of pension and social security to the senior citizens.

Table 1 Reliability of Religious Participation Scale and Life Satisfaction

Sl.No	Method	Religious Participation	Life Satisfaction
	Alpha	0.76	0.90
	Guttman Split-half	0.81	0.90
	P a r a l l e l		
	Estimated reliability of scale	0.76	0.90
	Unbiased estimate of reliability	0.76	0.90

Source: Computed

Table 2 Factor Matrix: Life Satisfaction

Sl.No	Item	Factor Loading
1	Achievements in Life	0.86
2	Feeling of Safety	0.86
3	Standard of Living	0.86
4	Future Security	0.84
5	Personal relationships	0.84
6	Feeling part of community	0.77
7	Spirituality or Religion	0.70
8	Health	0.47
	Eigen value	4.94
	% of Variance	61.79

Source: Computed

Table 3 Factor Matrix: Items of Religious Participation Scale

Sl.No	Item	Factor Loading
1	Participate in outreach programs of Church	0.75
2	Give Tithe in the Church	0.52
3	Attend church services on weekdays	0.81
4	Church programs and activities are an important part of my	0.64

	life	
5	Attend worship services on Sundays/ Saturdays	0.69
6	Attend morning prayer / mass service	0.61
	Eigen values	2.74
	% of Variance	45.64

Source: Computed

Table 1 Reliability of Religious Participation Scale and Life Satisfaction

Sl.No	Method	Religious Participation	Life Satisfaction
1	Alpha	0.76	0.90
2	Guttman Split-half	0.81	0.90
3	Parallel		
	Estimated reliability of scale	0.76	0.90
	Unbiased estimate of reliability	0.76	0.90

Source: Computed

Table 2 Factor Matrix: Items of Religious Participation Scale

Sl.No	Item	Factor Loading
1	Participate in outreach programs of Church	0.75
2	Give Tithe in the Church	0.52
3	Attend church services on weekdays	0.81
4	Church programs and activities are an important part of my life	0.64
5	Attend worship services on Sundays/ Saturdays	0.69
6	Attend morning prayer / mass service	0.61
	Eigen values	2.74
	% of Variance	45.64

Source: Computed

Table 3 Factor Matrix: Life Satisfaction

Sl.No	Item	Factor Loading
1	Achievements in Life	0.86
2	Feeling of Safety	0.86
3	Standard of Living	0.86
4	Future Security	0.84
5	Personal relationships	0.84
6	Feeling part of community	0.77
7	Spirituality or Religion	0.70
8	Health	0.47
	Eigen value	4.94
	% of Variance	61.79

Source: Computed

Table 4 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Sl.No	Characteristic	Gender		Total N = 288
		Male n = 159	Female n = 129	
I	Age Group			
	Young Old(60 - 70)	88 (55.3)	64 (49.6)	152 (52.8)
	Middle Old(70 - 80)	51 (32.1)	45 (34.9)	96 (33.3)
	Old Old(Above 80)	20 (12.6)	20 (15.5)	40 (13.9)
	<i>Mean Age</i>	71 ± 7.3	72 ± 8.0	71 ± 7.6
II	Marital Status			
	Never Married	1 (0.6)	9 (7.0)	10 (3.5)
	Married	118 (74.2)	49 (38.0)	167 (58.0)
	Divorced	4 (2.5)	9 (7.0)	13 (4.5)
	Widowed	30 (18.9)	62 (48.1)	92 (31.9)
	Remarried	6 (3.8)	0 (0.0)	6 (2.1)
III	Educational Status			
	Illiterate	3 (1.9)	17 (13.2)	20 (6.9)
	Literate	5 (3.1)	15 (11.6)	20 (6.9)
	Primary	77 (48.4)	70 (54.3)	147 (51.0)
	Middle School(4 - 7)	32 (20.1)	14 (10.9)	46 (16.0)
	High School(8 - 10)	25 (15.7)	11 (8.5)	36 (12.5)
	Higher Secondary and Above (11 - 17)	17 (10.7)	2 (1.6)	19 (6.6)
IV	Size of Family			

	Small(1-3)	40 (25.2)	30 (23.3)	70 (24.3)
	Medium(4 - 6)	65 (40.9)	63 (48.8)	128 (44.4)
	Large(7 and above)	54 (34.0)	36 (27.9)	90 (31.3)
V	Geographical Location			
	Rural	25 (15.7)	24 (18.6)	49 (17.0)
	Urban	134 (84.3)	105 (81.4)	239 (83.0)

Source: Computed

Table 5 Social and Economic Profile

Sl.No	Characteristic	Gender		Total N = 288
		Male n = 159	Female n = 129	
I	Denomination			
	Presbyterian	114 (71.7)	91 (70.5)	205 (71.2)
	United Pentecostal Church of Mizoram	18 (11.3)	16 (12.4)	34 (11.8)
	The Salvation Army	12 (7.5)	5 (3.9)	17 (5.9)
	Baptist Church of Mizoram	4 (2.5)	8 (6.2)	12 (4.2)
	The Roman Catholic	1 (0.6)	1 (0.8)	2 (0.7)
	Other Denominations	10 (6.3)	8 (6.2)	18 (6.3)
II	Monthly Household Income			
	Below 5000	9 (5.7)	13 (10.1)	22 (7.6)
	Rs. 5000 - 10000	18 (11.3)	18 (14.0)	36 (12.5)
	Rs.10000 - 20000	42 (26.4)	46 (35.7)	88 (30.6)

	Rs.20000 - 30000	48 (30.2)	27 (20.9)	75 (26.0)
	Rs. 30000 - 40000	20 (12.6)	14 (10.9)	34 (11.8)
	Rs. 40000 & above	22 (13.8)	11 (8.5)	33 (11.5)
III	Monthly Personal Income			
	Below 5000	69 (43.4)	98 (76.0)	167 (58.0)
	Rs.5000 - 10000	42 (26.4)	19 (14.7)	61 (21.2)
	Rs. 10000 - 15000	19 (11.9)	8 (6.2)	27 (9.4)
	Rs. 15000 - 20000	11 (6.9)	2 (1.6)	13 (4.5)
	Rs. 20000 - 25000	10 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	10 (3.5)
	Rs. 25000 & above	8 (5.0)	2 (1.6)	10 (3.5)

Source: Computed

Table 6 Gender and Religious Participation : Mean Difference

Sl.No		Gender				Difference		t
		Male		Female		Mean	Std. Error	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
1	Religious Participation	0.07	0.99	-0.08	1	0.15	0.12	1.23

Source: Computed

** P < 0.01

* P < 0.05

Table 7 Geographic Location and Religious Participation: Mean Difference

Sl.No		Geographical location				Difference		t
		Rural		Urban		Mean	Std. Error	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
1	Religious Participation	-0.36	1.22	0.07	0.93	-0.44	0.15	-2.83**

Source: Computed

** P < 0.01

* P < 0.05

Table 8 Determinants of Religious Participation: Regression Estimates

Sl.No	Explanatory Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		‘t’
		B	Std. Error	
1	Constant	-0.04	0.28	-0.14
2	Age Group	-0.15	0.09	-1.69
3	Gender(Female =1)	-0.04	0.14	-0.28
4	Denomination (Presbyterian = 1)	-0.04	0.13	-0.34
5	Living with Spouse (Yes =1)	0.12	0.14	0.86
6	Educational Status	0.03	0.06	0.45
7	Geographical Location(Rural =1)	-0.41	0.17	-2.48**
8	Size of Family	0.18	0.09	2.03*
9	Type of Family(Joint =1)	-0.04	0.10	-0.40
10	Monthly Household Income	0.06	0.05	1.12
11	Monthly Personal Income	-0.03	0.05	-0.55
	Std. Error of the Estimate	0.98		
	Adjusted R Square	0.05		
	F	2.38*		

Source: Computed ** P < 0.01

* P < 0.05

Table 9 Gender and Life Satisfaction: Mean Difference

Sl.No		Gender						‘t’
		Male		Female		Difference		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	Std. Error	
1	Life Satisfaction	0.02	0.99	-0.02	1	0.04	0.12	0.34

Source: Computed ** P < 0.01

* P < 0.05

Table 10 Geographic Location and Life Satisfaction: Mean Difference

Sl.No		Locality						t
		Rural		Urban		Difference		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	Std. Error	
2	Life Satisfaction	-1.33	0.71	0.27	0.82	-1.61	0.13	-12.83**

Source: Computed ** P < 0.01

* P < 0.05

Table 11 Determinants of Life Satisfaction: Regression Estimates

Sl.No	Explanatory Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
1	Constant	0.22	0.22	0.99	0.32
2	Age Group	-0.12	0.07	-1.66	0.10
3	Gender	0.04	0.11	0.40	0.69
4	Educational Status	-0.12	0.05	-2.36*	0.02
5	Living with Spouse	-0.14	0.11	-1.33	0.19
6	Size of Family	-0.09	0.07	-1.23	0.22
7	Type of Family	0.02	0.08	0.25	0.80
8	Denomination	0.22	0.10	2.19*	0.03
9	Geographical Location(Rural = 1)	-1.37	0.13	-10.34**	0.00
10	Monthly Household Income	0.09	0.04	2.16*	0.03
11	Monthly Personal Income	0.16	0.04	3.72**	0.00
12	Religious Participation	0.09	0.05	1.93*	0.05
13	Std. Error of the Estimate	0.77			
14	Adjusted R Square	0.40			
	F	18.54**			

Source: Computed ** P < 0.01

* P < 0.05

Table 12 Religious Participation and Life Satisfaction: Pearson Correlation

	Pearson's R
Correlation	0.19**
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00
N	288

Source: Computed ** P < 0.01

References

- Allick, D.M. (2012). Attitudes toward Religion and Spirituality in Social Work Practice. *Master of Social Work Clinical Research Papers*. Paper 137.
- Asher, M.B. (2001). Spirituality and Religion in Social Work Practice. *Social Work Today*, 1 (7).
- Berg, A.I. (2008). *Life Satisfaction in Late Life: Markers and Predictors of Level and Change among 80+ Year Olds*. (Doctoral Dissertation, University of Gothenburg, 2008).
- Carroll, M. (1998). Social work's conceptualization of spirituality. *Social Thought*, 18(2), 1-14.
- Cascio, T. (1998). Incorporating spirituality into social work practice: A review of what to do. *Families in Society: The Journal of Contemporary Human Services*. September-October, 523-531.
- Chen, C. (2001). Aging and life satisfaction. *Social Indicators Research*, Vol 54(51).
- Chadha, N.K. & Van Willigen, J. (1995). The Life Scale: The development of a measure of successful aging. *Indian Journal of Gerontology*, 9(3&4), 83-90.
- Cohen, S., Gottlieb, B. H., & Underwood, L. G. (2001). Social relationships and health: Challenges for measurement and intervention. *Advances in Mind Body Medicine*, 17(2), 129-141.
- Coholic, D. (2003a). Students and educator viewpoints on incorporating spirituality in social work pedagogy – an overview and discussion of research findings. *Currents: New Scholarship in Human Services*, 2(2). Retrieved from the University of Calgary Press website at http://fsw.ucalgary.ca/currents_prod_v1/articles/coholic_v2_n2.htm
- David, G. (2001). Aging, Religion and Spirituality: Advancing meaning in later life. *Social Thought*, 20(3-4), 129-140.
- Dey, A.B. (2003). *Aging in India: Situational analysis and planning for the future*. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. New Delhi: Ramko Press.
- Diener, E. (1984). Subjective well-being. *Psychological Bulletin*, 95(3), 542-575.
- Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., & Smith, H. L. (1999). Subjective well-being: Three decades of progress. *Psychological Bulletin*, 125(2), 276-302.
- Ellison, C.G. (1991). Religious Involvement and Subjective Wellbeing. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 32, 80-99.
- Ellison, C. G., & George, L. K. (1994). In Jain, M. & Purohit, P. (2006). Spiritual Intelligence: A Contemporary Concern with Regard to Living Status of the Senior Citizens. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 32(3), 227 – 233.
- Ellison, C.G. & Linda K.G. (1994). Religious Involvement, Social Ties, and Social Support in a Southeastern Community. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 33, 46-61.
- Ellor, J. W., & McGregor, J. A. (2011). Reflection on the words 'Religion,' 'Spiritual Well-Being,' and 'Spirituality'. *Journal of Religion, Spirituality and Aging*, 23, 275-278. doi:10.1080/15528030.2011.603074

Social Work Journal (Bi-annual), Dept. of Social Work, AUS

- Freund, A. M., & Baltes, P. B. (1998). Selection, optimization, and compensation as strategies of life management: correlations with subjective indicators of successful aging. *Psychology and Aging, 13*(4), 531-543.
- Furness, S. & Giligan, P. (2010). Social Work, Religion and Belief: Developing a framework for Practice. *British Journal of Social Work, 40*, 2185–2202. doi:10.1093/bjsw/bcp159.
- Gilbert, M.C. (2000). Spirituality in social work groups: Practitioners speak out. *Social Work with Groups, 22*(4), 67-84.
- Hamarat, E., Thompson, D., Aysan, F., Steele, D., Matheny, K., & Simons, C. (2002). Age differences in coping resources and satisfaction with life among middle-aged, young old, and oldest-old adults. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology; Child Behavior, Animal Behavior, and Comparative Psychology, 163*(3), 360-367.
- Hodge, D.R. (2003). The Intrinsic Spirituality Scale: A new six-item instrument for assessing the salience of spirituality as a motivational construct. *Journal of Social Service Research, 30*(1), 41-60.
- Irudaya-Rajan, S., Misra, U.S., & Sarma, P.S. (2001). Health concerns among India's elderly. *International Journal of Aging and Human Development, 53*, 191-204.
- Kaplan, A. J., & Dziegielewski, S. F. (1999). Graduate social work students' attitudes and behaviors toward spirituality and religion: issues for education and practice. *Social Work & Christianity, 26*(1), 25-39.
- Krause, N. (2003). Religious Meaning and Subjective Well-Being in Late Life. *Journal of Gerontology: Social Sciences, 58B*, S160–S170.
- Krause, N & Wulff, K.M. (2005). Church-Based Social Ties, a Sense of Belonging in a Congregation, and Physical Health Status. *International Journal for the Psychology of Religion, 15*,73–93.
- Larsen, K. (2010). *How spiritual are social workers? an exploration of social work practitioners' personal spiritual beliefs, attitudes, and practices*. Univ. of Maryland at Baltimore). , 155-175. Retrieved from <http://ezproxy.stthomas.edu/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=sw&AN=80312&site=ehost-live>
- Lezotte, E. (2010). Spirituality and Social Work. Focus Ce Course.
- Lim, C. & Putnam, R.D. (2010). Religion, Social Networks and Life Satisfaction. *American Sociological Review, 75*(6), 914–933.
- Markides, K. S., & Martin, H. W. (1979). A causal model of life satisfaction among the elderly. *Journals of Gerontology, 34*(1), 86-93.
- Mehta, K.K. (1997). The impact of Religious Beliefs and Practices on Aging : A cross-cultural comparison. *Journal Of Aging Studies, 11*(2), 101-114.
- Melia, S. P. (2001). Older women find that prayer matures along with them. *Aging & Spirituality, 13* (1), 1, 7. Miltiades, H. B., & Pruchno, R. (2002). The effect of religious

- coping on caregiving appraisals of mothers of adults with developmental disabilities. *The Gerontologist*, 42(1), 82-91.
- Mercier, C., Peladeau, N., & Tempier, R. (1998). Age, gender and quality of life. *Community Mental Health Journal*, 34(5), 487-500.
- Morse, C. K., & Wisocki, P. A. (1987). Importance of religiosity to elderly adjustment. *Journal of Religion & Aging*, 4 (1), 15-26.
- Mroczek, D. K., & Spiro, A., 3rd. (2005). Change in life satisfaction during adulthood: findings from the veterans affairs normative aging study. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 88(1), 189-202.
- Murtagh, K. N., & Hubert, H. B. (2004). Gender differences in physical disability among an elderly cohort. *American Journal of Public Health*, 94(8), 1406-1411.
- Pinquart, M., & Sorensen, S. (2000). Influences of socioeconomic status, social network, and competence on subjective well-being in later life: a meta-analysis. *Psychology and Aging*, 15(2), 187-224.
- Prenda, K. M., & Lachman, M. E. (2001). Planning for the future: a life management strategy for increasing control and life satisfaction in adulthood. *Psychology and Aging*, 16(2), 206-216.
- Revicki, D. A., & Mitchell, J. P. (1990). Strain, social support, and mental health in rural elderly individuals. *Journal of Gerontology*, 45(6), S267-274.
- Sermabeikian, P. (1992). Our Clients, Ourselves: The Spiritual Perspective and Social Work Practice. *National Association of Social Workers, Inc.*, 178-183.
- Shin, D. C., & Johnson, D. M. (1978). Avowed happiness as an overall assessment of the quality of life. *Social Indicators Research*, 5, 475-492.
- Van Hook, M., Hugen, B. & Aguilar, M. (Eds.) (2001). Spirituality within Religious Traditions in Social Work Practice. Pacific Grove, CA: Brooks/Cole.